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Deleted: WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism in Academic Writing (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
6. CMS for Research and Academic Writing (EUCLID 2024, 43-56)

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WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

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1) INTRODUCTION

As any journey begins, it is evident for people to be high, but as the journey progresses, it brings the reality of how tough it could be. The journey of my Doctoral Program is similar, wherein I got the hang of it after the admission process. It stopped me thinking, contemplating, and checking if I was headed in the right direction. Today, I have crossed that phase wherein I have rediscovered myself and am fully committed to this learning journey, no matter how challenging it may be. I have realized there is always something to learn, unlearn, and relearn. Period 1 of ACA-401D helps understand different types of essays, focusing on academic essays, how to write one, and the nuances to be followed while writing a good one. In the era of technological advancement with the arrival of Large Language Models, the task of learning to write good essays is slowly disappearing, as giving a couple of prompts to any AI (Artificial Intelligence) tool can provide a well-fabricated essay that could be easily used. This also raises the question of how an individual's ethics prevent them from doing so.

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Period 1 of this paper helped me understand different aspects of Essay writing by classifying the types of essays, the importance of punctuation, the differences between

American and British English, how to give credit to the authors, and how to avoid plagiarism. I learned about using different writing styles used worldwide for citing and using Style Guide while writing an Essay. The paper also helped me understand the usage of abbreviations and expressions that could be non-native to English.

2) DIFFERENT TYPES OF ESSAYS

Essays could range from narrative to descriptive to argumentative, focusing on academic or non-academic purposes. Academic essays constitute scholarly writing, serving nonfictional works to present research findings or analyses. Academic essays have a formal prose register that incorporates citations and references and utilizes established rhetorical moves to clarify the scope and relevance of the research. The writing process should follow these critical steps:

- starting early to allow ample time for reading and thinking
- clearly defining the essay question or topic
- drafting a preliminary plan to organize ideas and research.

Comprehensive research is essential, which prompts writers to evaluate what they know, identify necessary readings, and determine the usefulness of their sources in supporting the arguments. Research on the topic provides the knowledge and evidence required to develop a solid essay and articulate informed responses. The reading should be supported by taking detailed notes on the subject and including bibliographic information needed for proper citation. Organizing ideas into a structured essay plan will help clarify the response to the essay question, allowing the selection of pertinent evidence and examples. The whole process should bring creative and critical thinking, ensuring the essay reflects a balanced exploration of a wide range of viewpoints, ultimately leading to a well-reasoned conclusion.

The writing of an essay begins with producing a first draft that adheres to a clear structure and serves as the foundation for further refinement through editing. The structure of any essay should contain three parts: an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. The introduction should present the topic broadly before narrowing it down to the problem statement and a brief overview of the essay's main points. The body comprises well-structured paragraphs, supported by incorporating evidence, examples, and authoritative quotes, with each section focusing on a single main idea. The conclusion summarizes the essential findings and ascertains the results without introducing new information. During the writing process, it is crucial to stay focused on the essay topic, engage in critical analysis, and ensure proper referencing to uphold academic integrity. After completing the draft, allowing time before editing can provide fresh insights for improvement, ensuring the final submission is coherent and well-organized.

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The usage of stylistic variety is essential to avoid monotonous sentence structures and improve the essay quality. The assertions must be supported with relevant evidence when attributing views to philosophers. The direct use of authors' quotes should be minimized; paraphrasing critical points is advisable. The ideas on the topic should be engaged thoughtfully, thereby striking a balance to ensure coherence and considering how the readers might respond. The usage of the tense should be in the first person. There should be sufficient time to carefully edit and revise the essay, which will significantly improve the quality of the essay.

3) **SIGNIFICANCE OF PUNCTUATION**

The importance of punctuation can never be undermined while writing an essay. The essence of punctuation is based on minimal, clear, and necessary symbols that help organize and clarify sentence meaning. The general rule in punctuation is to use them sparingly to ensure clarity without overcomplicating the text. Some of the standard punctuation and their usage are discussed below:

- Apostrophe (') is used to indicate possession of an object. Depending on the singularity and plurality of the word, it should be used effectively
- Brackets (Square, Round, Angle, Curly) are used to add additional information, comments, translations, etc.
- Bullet Point is used to grab the reader's attention and highlight the main point
- Colon (:) is used to introduce a sub-clause that follows logically from the text before it, while a semi-colon (;) is used to link two related parts of independent clauses
- Comma (,) is used to separate two nouns or a phrase and a clause
- En Dash (–) shows the relationship between two words, dates, or numbers
- Em Dash (—) is used to separate certain words from the rest of the sentence and can sometimes replace commas, colons, and parentheses
- Hyphen (-) connects compound words, word elements, and numbers¹
- Ellipsis (...) is used to indicate some text is missing

¹ Danielle, "Grammarist."

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- Full stop (.), exclamation mark (!), and Question mark (?): Either of the one is used at the end of a sentence to indicate a sentence closure
- Quotations (' or ") are used to refer to a direct speech or a quote within

Using a structured approach to punctuation allows for consistent, clear, and purposeful punctuation in writing.

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

The growth of the English language has been continuous since the days of its origin. People living in different parts of the world have generously contributed words to the English dictionary. In the modern world, the language is identified with two variants: American and British English. The variations between the two are broadly classified as:

- Words with the exact spelling but different pronunciation
- Words with a different spelling but the same pronunciation
- Words representing the same term with similar spelling and pronunciation
- Same words with different or additional meanings

The differences have been identified in grammar, syntax, and punctuation. The difference in the usage of periods and commas is significant, with American English (AE) placing them inside closing quotation marks. In contrast, in British English (BE), they are placed outside quotation marks. Similarly, AE favors double quotation for initial quotation and single for quotation inside quotation while the reverse is followed in BE.

The differences in date formatting are similar, with the BE following DD/MM/YYYY while AE following MM/DD/YYYY. If this is not correctly understood, it can create ambiguity. The punctuation differences between American and British English reflect diverse linguistic traditions and typesetting practices that have evolved over time. Though the differences seem to be minor, these influence how written material is interpreted and perceived. Understanding these distinctions is essential, as writers and readers increasingly encounter both American and British conventions interchangeably.

5) PLAGIARISM IN ACADEMIC WRITING

While writing academic papers, it is the responsibility of the author to avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism in any form, using another person's words, ideas, or creative work without giving proper credit to the original author or getting someone else to write a paper, is offensive. Plagiarism is a form of intellectual theft that undermines the integrity of the writer and the academic community.

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The necessity to give credit to the author is of utmost importance when using their words, ideas, data, or visuals. It could be a quote, paraphrased content, or graphs/diagrams. Proper citation helps respect the original creator and helps readers trace the information back to its source, enhancing the credibility of the writer's work. Acknowledging sources adds depth to a paper by showing the writer's engagement with existing research, allowing them to build upon ideas and contribute to scholarly conversations. The mentioning of the source of information demonstrates honesty, respect for intellectual property, and a commitment to academic integrity.

There are two significant methods of citing

- In-text citation: In-text citing is used to cite quotations and paraphrases. Quotations are the exact words of an author, while paraphrases are the ideas that an author has produced written in their own words.
- List of works cited: The list of works cited is the 'bibliography' or the 'references' listed at the end of the book.

The situations that do not need to be cited are those where the information written is common knowledge that could be found in multiple places. In conclusion, avoiding plagiarism is fundamental in academic writing, as it upholds integrity, respects the work of others, and maintains trust within the academic community. By carefully citing sources, writers avoid plagiarism and enhance their credibility, thereby contributing to responsible research practices.

6) THE ROLE OF STYLE GUIDES IN WRITING

A style guide is a foundational tool that ensures consistency, coherence, and quality across written content. EUCLID recommends using the Chicago (Turabian) style, though other internationally recognized formats are also accepted. The emphasis on a uniform standard exemplifies how style guides can streamline the writing process and improve readability. A style guide documents the preferred approach to writing, which is essential for types of content where consistency is critical, such as technical, business, and journalistic writing. When multiple authors contribute to a project, a style guide ensures that each piece aligns with the overall tone and standard of the publication, organization, or brand. By applying a uniform set of rules, style guides prevent individual writing styles from overshadowing the intended voice of the company or publication. This enables the final output to be polished and unified, reflecting a single, cohesive identity rather than the personal preferences of various authors.

The professionals in technical writing rely on style guides, while creative writers who value flexibility tend to avoid them. For example, a technical writer may need to adhere to a specific style guide for a client to ensure that content remains consistent with other materials the client already uses. Style guides help bridge the gap between creativity and clarity, allowing writers to focus on their content while upholding agreed-upon standards.

The absence of a single authoritative style standard for all English writing means that stylistic choices, from vocabulary to tone, often differ across guides. The style guides do more than enforce correct punctuation and grammar; they encompass broader stylistic elements such as formatting, voice, and structure. By setting these guidelines, style guides enable writers to communicate clearly and consistently within the unique frameworks to different audiences. In conclusion, a style guide is mandatory to ensure uniformity and professionalism in written communication. The establishment of clear stylistic expectations enhances the quality of written work, promotes brand coherence, and provides structure without stifling creativity. In any professional setting, adhering to a style guide allows for a more cohesive and polished final product, fostering both clarity and credibility.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE FOR RESEARCH AND ACADEMIC WRITING

The Chicago Style, widely used in formatting books and research papers, is a comprehensive guide published by the University of Chicago Press. The CMS and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations provide detailed guidelines for scholarly and professional writing, making it one of the most used formatting styles. Although slightly adapted for academic settings, Turabian's guide is essentially the Chicago Style, making "Turabian style" a synonym for Chicago Style in the context of research papers and theses.

The Chicago Style is known for its clarity and attention to detail, covering a wide range of grammar, punctuation, and citation rules. It is highly used in disciplines like history, literature, and the arts, where authors need a versatile format to cite various source types. CMS style can accommodate the "notes and bibliography" format for footnotes and endnotes, which is popular in humanities fields. The "author-date" format for in-text citations is preferred in the sciences and social sciences. This flexibility allows writers to choose the CMS format that best suits their research and disciplinary needs, making the CMS one of the most adaptable and user-friendly styles in academic writing.

The CMS format delves deeply into how abbreviations must be used along with the proper punctuation. Abbreviations should be used after clear initialization by placing it in parentheses. There are specific rules around how Geographical terms, like the names of countries, states, etc., should be written. The Chicago Style specifies a clear page layout structure, enhancing readability and presentation. Papers should be double-spaced, using a legible 12-point font like Times New Roman, with one-inch margins on all sides. Each new section or chapter generally begins on a new page, following the style's organized and structured presentation approach. Furthermore, the text should be left-aligned, with the first line of each paragraph indented by one-half inch. The page numbers are placed in the upper right-hand corner, providing a professional and easily navigable layout.

Chicago Style's treatment of endnotes and footnotes is one of its defining features. They allow the author to provide supplementary information and references

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without interrupting the flow of the main text. The note is formatted with the author's name, title of the work, publication details, and relevant page numbers. If the same source is cited repeatedly, shortened citations are used in subsequent notes to maintain a clear and concise format. Bibliography entries at the end of the document include all works referenced.

8) CONCLUSION

Learning to write a good essay is of immense importance, which was learned during this period. The different aspects to be considered while writing an essay are understood towards the end of this period. The importance of using a style guide, proper citing, and avoiding plagiarism has been learned. During this process, I have also improved my understanding of using tools like Zotero, Grammarly, and MS Word. The completion of this period has given me enough confidence to pursue further.

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